

A Study on Nutritional Assessment and Adulteration of Raw and Pasteurized Milk Collected from Local Markets in Dhaka City

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Milk is one of the most valuable and regularly consumable foods. Recently, raw milk adulteration is a burning issue in Bangladesh. The present investigation was an experimental study, conducted to evaluate the nutritional quality and qualitative detection of adulterants in both raw and pasteurized milk. A total number of 20 milk samples were collected from local markets of Dhaka and its nearest areas. Obtained data was compared with the standard values of BSTI and Food Composition Table for Bangladesh. The results revealed that proximate analysis such as Fat (3.17%, 4.37%, 3.53%), Protein (3.26%, 3.99%, 3.34%) and Lactose (4.17%, 4.23%, 4.30%) for milk samples collected from milkmen, dairy farm; and for pasteurized milk samples respectively. While the determination of other parameters gave the data that Titratable acidity (0.18%, 0.17%, 0.16%), Cholesterol (8.95 mg/100g, 7.95 mg/100g, 0.589 mg/100g) and Calcium (170.40 mg/100g, 328.09 mg/100g, 266.27 mg/100g) for milk samples collected from milkmen, dairy farm; and pasteurize milk samples respectively. Majority of the samples' nutrient content were as per the standard values. About 70% samples were adulterated with neutralizers and 30% were adulterated with skimmed milk powder. Detergent and Starch showed no positive test result in all the samples. This study concluded that samples collected from dairy farm contained higher nutritive elements than pasteurize milk and the samples of milkmen. Samples collected from milkmen and pasteurize milks were similarly adulterated with neutralizers.

Keywords: ADULTERATION, RAW MILK, PASTEURIZE MILK, NUTRITIONAL ASSESSMENT, CALCIUM, CHOLESTEROL.

Introduction

Milk is one of the most precious natural and regularly consumable foods (Maboodet al., 2017), considered as the best sources for protein, fat, carbohydrate, vitamin and minerals (Azad and Ahmed, 2016) such as copper, zinc, manganese and iron (Ojha et al., 2017). According to Brandaoet al. (2017), milk-fat contains a wide

type of fatty acids and high content of short-chain volatile fatty acids that helps in lactose assimilation (Hasan et al., 2017). Galactose is essential for the central nervous system (Sarker, 2017) and helps to improve calcium utilization in the body (Hasan et al., 2017). Cow's milk contains 3 times higher glutamic acid than in human milk, responsible for the reduction of cholesterol level in blood (Hasan and Rakib, 2016).

Nowadays, Food adulteration especially raw milk is becoming a burning issue (Bari et al., 2015) in developing countries due to lack of monitoring and policies (Azad and Ahmed, 2016). According to Reddy et al. (2017), possible reasons included- increased demand, growth in competition in dairy industry and financial profits. Moonajilinet al.(2018) mentioned some of the major adulterants having serious adverse health effect like urea, formalin, detergents, ammonium sulphate, boric acid, caustic soda, benzoic acid, salicylic acid, hydrogen peroxide, sugars and melamine. Other adulterants include- starch, chlorine, hydrated lime, sodium carbonate and various antibiotics; sugar, water, salt (Reddy et al., 2017). Preliminary Report on Household Income and Expenditure Survey 2016 showed that the total daily consumption of milk and milk products is reduced to 27.31 g/day in 2016 from 33.72 g/day in 2010 nationally (BBS, 2017). About 68% milk delivered to the consumers is not as per standards (Reddy et al., 2017). Moonajilinet al. (2018) reported about 23% people consumed powder milk, 64.7% people consumed loose milk and 45% people consumed pasteurized milk, 87.8% respondents were strongly agreed that milk adulteration has harmful effects on health. Some common adulterants and their effects on health are mentioned in Table-1. This study was conducted to evaluate nutritional quality and to determine various types of adulterants added in both raw and pasteurize milk samples.

Table – 1: Reasons of Adding Adulterants and Their Adverse Health Effects on Human Body.

Adulterants	Reason of Use	Effects on Health	Reference
<p align="center">Neutralizers (NaOH, Na₂CO₃, NaHCO₃)</p>	<p align="center">For maintaining the pH and acidity values of badly preserved milk.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gastrointestinal problems including Gastric ulcers, Diarrhea, Colon ulcers. • Electrolyte disturbances in human, Disruptions of hormone signaling that regulates development and Reproduction. • Sodium hydroxide also interrupted lysine (an essential amino acid in milk) utilization in the body, which is mostly needed by the growing babies. 	<p align="center">Reddy et al., 2017; Navale and Gupta (2016); Singuluri and Sukumaran (2014); Ayub et al., 2007</p>

Detergent	To emulsify and liquefy the oil in water giving a foamy solution, To maintain the white color of milk, To giving it a frothy solution, To increase foamy texture.	Gastro-intestinal complications and Breast cancer	Kaur et al., 2018 Navale and Gupta (2016); Singuluri and Sukumaran (2014);
Starch	Used to increase solid-non-fat (SNF). Apart from the starch, cereal flours or arrowroot are added to make up the density of milk to prevent detection of added water	High amounts of starch in milk can cause Diarrhea due to the effects of undigested starch in colon and this extra accumulated starch in the body may seems to be very fatal for diabetic patients.	Navale and Gupta (2016) Singuluri and Sukumaran (2014);
Skimmed milk powder	for economic profit, when a country has excess lower dried powder milk	-	Guan et al., (2005)

Materials and methods

Study Design and Area

An experimental study was carried out for the analysis of both raw milk and pasteurize milk. Raw milk samples were obtained from different parts of Dhaka city (Mohammadpur and Keranigonj) and its surrounding areas (Savar and Narayanaganj). Pasteurize milk samples were purchased from different general stores inside Dhaka.

Sample Collection

A total number of 20 milk samples were collected for this study. About 13 different samples each containing 1 liter of raw milk from 7 several milkmen and from 6 other dairy farms, were obtained from different parts of Dhaka city and its surrounding areas. And, 7 different pasteurize milk samples were collected for this study.

Sample Preservation and Transportation

The raw milk samples were collected in sterilized bottles. Both raw and pasteurize milk samples were kept into deep freeze immediately after collection and transported to the laboratory.

Chemicals and Reagents

All the chemicals and reagents including standards chemicals such as – Sulfuric acid (95-97%) (Prod. No. 258105), Boric acid, Iodine (Standard), Potassium iodide (Prod. No. 1.05040), Ethanol (Prod. No.32205), Sodium hydroxide (Prod. No. 221465), Potassium hydroxide (Prod. No. 1.05033), Phenolphthalein (pH 8.3-10.0), Hydrochloric acid (Prod. No. 84429), Rosalic acid powder (C₁₉H₁₄O₃), Methylene blue dye (Prod. No. M9140), Chloroform (Prod. No. 1.02431), Diethyl ether (Prod. No. 1.00921), Petroleum benzene (Prod. No. 1.01775), Potassium permanganate, Sodium hydrogen carbonate (Prod. No. 10247) etc. were purchased from Merck KGaA, Germany, Sigma Chemical Co. (St Louis, MO, USA). Other chemicals used were all of analytical reagents. Used water was re-distilled water.

Physical and Chemical Analysis

Different tests related to physical and chemical properties analysis and adulterants detection were carried out for determining quality status and adulteration. Density of the milk was determined by the lactometer test (Mamun et al., 2016). Specific gravity of milk was calculated according to the formula given by Tesfayet al., 2015. Milk fat was determined according to the gravimetric Rose-Gottlieb Method with slightly modification (Nazim et al., 2013). The estimation of protein was performed by micro-Kjeldahl Method described as Nazim et al., 2013. This method is done in three steps- Digestion, Distillation and Titration. According to the methods performed by Nazim et al. (2013), Titratable acidity, Ash, Lactose, Total milk solid was determined. The Solid Non Fat was calculated by subtracting the Fat from the Total Milk Solid (Getachew, 2003). Energy was calculated according to the General Atwater Method described by Charrondiere et al., in 2004. Calcium and Cholesterol content was estimated by using UV-Spectrophotometric Method (Model: SHIMADZU, UV-1800) described by Satteret al. (2013).

Detection of Adulterants:

Neutralizers: Take 5 ml suspected milk sample and added 5 ml of 95% Ethanol solution in it. A few drops of 0.1% Rosalic acid solution was added drop by drop. Rose red color appears when neutralizers are present in the sample whereas absence of neutralizers shows only a brown color. The detection limit of this process is 0.1% NaOH, 0.1% Na₂CO₃ and 0.2% NaHCO₃ (FSSAI, 2015).

Detergent: Take 1 ml of sample and added 1 ml of methylene blue dye and 2 ml of Chloroform in it. Vortex the test tube contents for about 15 minutes and centrifuge it at 1100 rpm for 3-5 minutes. Development of more intense blue color in the lower layer indicates the presence of detergent in the milk sample. The detection limit of this process is 0.05% (FSSAI, 2015).

Starch: Take 5ml sample in a test tube and boil. Cool and add 1-2 drops of Iodine Solution. Development of blue color indicates the presence of starch in the sample. The detection limit of this process is 0.02% (FSSAI, 2015).

Skimmed milk powder: The sample was heated to 37°C - 40°C and kept for cooling to room temperature (26°C – 28°C). Take 5 ml prepared sample in a test tube and pounded properly. Then Nitric acid was added

into it drop by drop. Development of orange color indicates that the sample is adulterated with skimmed milk powder and development of yellow color shows that the sample is not adulterated with skimmed milk powder (Bari et al., 2015).

Statistical Analysis

The data were recorded, tabulated and categorized in the Microsoft Office Excel Sheet (2007) and finally statistically analysis was carried out by using SPSS (version 20.0) programme.

Results and discussion

Table - 2: Comparison of Physiological and Chemical Concentrations among Raw cow's milk obtained from Dairy farms (n=6) & Milkmen (n=7); and Pasteurize milks (n=7).

Parameters / Variables	Raw cow's Milk from Milkmen (n=7)	Raw cow's Milk from Dairy Farms (n=6)	Pasteurized Milk (n=7)
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD
Density (g/ml)	1029 \pm 1.83	1029.83 \pm 1.17	1027 \pm 2.29
Specific gravity	1.029 \pm 0.001	1.029 \pm 0.001	1.027 \pm 0.002
Titrateable Acidity (%)	0.18 \pm 0.04	0.17 \pm 0.02	0.16 \pm 0.02
Ash (%)	0.66 \pm 0.05	0.69 \pm 0.03	0.63 \pm 0.03
Protein (%)	3.26 \pm 0.29	3.99 \pm 0.29	3.34 \pm 0.11
Lactose (%)	4.17 \pm 0.32	4.23 \pm 0.28	4.30 \pm 0.34
Fat (%)	3.17 \pm 0.53	4.37 \pm 1.12	3.53 \pm 0.11
Solid Non Fat (%)	8.33 \pm 0.798	8.73 \pm 0.58	8.66 \pm 0.79
Total Solid (%)	11.49 \pm 1.25	13.10 \pm 1.52	11.98 \pm 0.56
Cholesterol (mg/100g)	8.95 \pm 3.14	7.95 \pm 2.56	0.589 \pm 1.47
Calcium (mg/100g)	170.40 \pm 36.46	328.09 \pm 220.44	266.27 \pm 143.27
Energy (Kcal)	57.87 \pm 6.56	72.20 \pm 9.67	62.04 \pm 2.32

Results were expressed as Mean \pm SD

Density

Present study shows (Table – 2) the mean Density of pasteurize milk was not as per the BSTI(2002) standards (1028-1032 g/ml) but samples collected from milkmen and dairy farm was within the BSTI(1988) standard range.

Specific gravity

Kader et al. (2015) reported that the specific gravity of cow's milk varied from 1.026 to 1.034 within an average of 1.031. Islam et al. (1984) found a higher specific gravity of cow's milk from BAU Dairy Farm than local markets. Table-2 showed that the mean specific gravity of raw milk in this study was as per the BSTI standard (1.028-1.032) level. It is clearly indicating, milk samples were free from water adulteration that also agreed with the study of Hasan and Rakib (2016). Pasteurize milk showed lower specific gravity than

the standard range.

Titratable Acidity

In 2016, [Uddin et al.](#) reported the maximum acidity percentage in Mymensingh sadar bazaar that was 0.18 ± 0.02 . [Hasan and Rakib \(2016\)](#) reported normal acidity values for their experimental samples. [Hasan et al. \(2017\)](#) also found that the average of acidity milk samples collected from Bangladesh Agricultural University Dairy Farm (different Hall milk suppliers and vendors) were 0.15%, 0.16%, and 0.15% respectively. In present study (Table – 2), it was found that the average titratable acidity (%) of both raw and pasteurize milk was not as per the BSTI standard value (maximum 0.15%). According to [Rahman et al. \(2017\)](#), the percentage of the acidity is positively correlated with SNF content in milk.

Ash Content

[Hasan and Rakib \(2016\)](#) mentioned that [Amin \(2005\)](#) in his study found the average ash content of milk was 0.67% which was similar to the result of [Uddin et al., 2016](#). In the study of [Rahman et al. \(2017\)](#) the ash content of the milk samples collected from BAU Shesh more, BAU KR market, train going vendor, sweetmeat shop and Dhudmohol were 0.49 ± 0.02 , 0.64 ± 0.02 , 0.66 ± 0.01 , 0.69 ± 0.00 and 0.55 ± 0.03 , respectively. From Table – 2, it is showed that the mean ash content (%) of raw milk in this study was 0.66 ± 0.05 , 0.69 ± 0.03 that is as per the BSTI standard (minimum 0.7%) value but pasteurize milk contains slightly lower ash content (0.63 ± 0.03).

Protein Content

[Uddin et al. \(2016\)](#) reported an average protein value of milk samples collected from local markets of Mymensingh sadar was 3.34%, 3.29%, 3.47% and 3.39%, respectively. [Khatun et al. \(2018\)](#) showed that milk from west region of Bangladesh contains higher content of protein that is 4.06%. The protein content of the milk samples of [Rahman et al. \(2017\)](#) was 1.97%, 2.87%, 2.79%, 3.27% and 2.42% respectively. Present study (Table – 2) revealed that the average protein content (%) was as per the BSTI standards (minimum 3.3%) for both raw and pasteurize milk.

Lactose Content

The principal milk carbohydrate is lactose. The mean lactose content (%) of both raw and pasteurize milk in this study (Table – 2) was slightly lower than that of the BSTI standard value (minimum 4.4%). In 2014, [Rahman et al.](#) reported 5.29% of lactose in milk from Western and Central part of Bangladesh which was higher than the results of this study. [Hasan and Rakib \(2016\)](#) mentioned that the lactose content of collected raw milk samples were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Fat Content

[Uddin et al. \(2016\)](#) reported that the fat content of milk was lower in Mymensingh sadar bazaar milk samples. Again [Islam et al. \(2013\)](#) found higher fat content (4.0, 3.2 and 4.9%) in the milk of MuktagachaUpazila. The

average fat content (%) of raw milk from milkmen in this research work was found not to be satisfactory compared to the BSTI standard (minimum 3.5%) but fat content of milk from dairy farms and pasteurize milks was as per standard value (Table – 2).

Solid Non Fat Content

[Khatun et al. \(2018\)](#) found 9.87%, 10.83% and 10.19% of SNF content in the raw milk samples collected from south-central, west and North-West zone of Bangladesh. Again [Islam et al. \(2008\)](#) reported in their study, the average SNF percentage of milk of local cows was 8.7%. In the present study (Table – 2), the average Solid Non Fat content (%) of milk from dairy farms and pasteurize milk was as per the BSTI standards (minimum 8.4%) but samples from milkmen showed slightly lower average of SNF than the standard value.

Total Milk Solid Content

[Islam et al. \(1984\)](#) found lower total solid percentage in milk from local markets. [Islam et al. \(2008\)](#) studied the milk quality of local cows in BAU Dairy Farm and reported 14.25% total solids content of cow's milk. Present study showed, the average total milk solid content was $11.49 \pm 1.25\%$, $13.10 \pm 1.52\%$ and $11.98 \pm 0.56\%$ for milk from milkmen, dairy farms and pasteurize milks (Table – 2). [Tesfay et al.\(2015\)](#) reported that the total solid content of milk samples collected from dairy farms was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than the milk samples from milkmen and the pasteurized milk.

Cholesterol Content

The present study estimated an average cholesterol content of milk samples from milkmen, dairy farms and pasteurize milk and that was 8.95 ± 3.14 , 7.95 ± 2.56 and 0.589 ± 1.47 mg/100g respectively (Table – 2). We found less cholesterol content than the study of [Sayem \(1986\)](#) that was approximate 12 mg/100g of milk respectively.

Calcium Content

The average calcium content (mg/100g) in this study was 170 ± 36.46 , 328.09 ± 220.44 and 266.27 ± 143.27 for milk from milkmen, dairy farms and pasteurize milk (Table – 2). Pasteurize milks contained higher level of calcium than the value estimated by [Shaheen et al., 2014](#).

Energy

Present study (Table – 2) showed an average energy content (Kcal) of milk that is 57.87 ± 6.56 for milkmen, 72.20 ± 9.67 for dairy farms and 62.04 ± 2.32 for pasteurize milk samples. Pasteurize milk showed slightly lower average energy than the value estimated by [Shaheen et al., 2014](#) that is 63 Kcal.

Table – 3: Presence of Adulterants (%) in the Raw Milk and Pasteurize Milk Samples.

Different types of Adulterants	Neutralizers (n=20)	Detergent (n=20)	Skimmed Milk Powder (n=20)	Starch (n=20)
Percentage (%) of Adulterants present in both Raw milk and Pasteurize milk samples	70	0	30	0

Results were expressed as frequency distribution

Table – 4: Comparison of Presence of Adulterants (%) among Raw cow's milk obtained from Dairy farms (n=6) & Milkmen (n=7); and Pasteurize milk (n=7) Samples.

Different types of Adulterants	Raw Milk from Milkmen (n=7)		Raw Milk from Dairy Farms (n=6)		Pasteurized Milks (n=7)	
	Positive (%)	Negative (%)	Positive (%)	Negative (%)	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
Neutralizers	71.4	28.6	66.7	33.3	71.4	28.6
Skimmed Milk Powder	42.9	57.1	50	50	0	100
Detergent	0	100	0	100	0	100
Starch	0	100	0	100	0	100

Results were expressed as frequency distribution

Neutralizers

Ojha et al. (2017) reported that all the raw milk samples of their study were tested negative for Neutralizers. Chanda et al. (2012) found about 20% samples of their samples were detected as Neutralizers positive in raw milk samples. About 70% samples were adulterated with Neutralizers in this study (Table – 3). The present result disclosed (Table – 4) that both raw and pasteurize milk samples were adulterated with Neutralizers.

Starch

Islam et al. (2013) in his study revealed that no milk was adulterated with starch. In 2015, Bari et al. found 66.67% of the milk samples collected from Tangail Town and Santosh Bazar, 50% samples from Porabari bazaar and Bajitpur Bazar was adulterated with starch. On average, 12% milk samples were found to be adulterated with starch in the study of Chanda et al. (2012). Study of Nayak (2017) in India confirmed only 10% samples were adulterated with starch. In this study, samples gave 100% negative test result for starch (Table – 3) which found to be satisfactory compared to the study of Islam et al., 2013; Paul et al., 2018; Rahman et al., 2017 and Uddin et al., 2016. From Table-4, the result displays that both raw and pasteurize milk samples were not adulterated with Starch.

Skimmed Milk Powder

In 2015, [Bari et al.](#) found 50.002% samples were adulterated with Skim milk powder. On average, 14% raw milk samples were detected as skimmed milk powder positive in the study of [Chanda et al. \(2012\)](#). [Koberet al., 2015](#) and [Paul et al., 2018](#) found 100% negative test result for skimmed milk powder in raw milk samples. About 30% milk samples were adulterated with Skimmed milk powder in this study (Table – 3). From Table-4, present study found that raw milk samples were adulterated with extra Skimmed milk powder and pasteurize milk was free of extra skimmed milk powder.

Detergent

[Nayak \(2017\)](#) reported no milk samples were detected as detergent positive in his study. In the present study, Detergent was not present in any of the milk samples (Table – 3,4) that agreed to the statement of [Nayak \(2017\)](#).

Conclusion

Milk is an eminent source of nutrition associated with good health. Due to increasing demand regarding inadequate supply; and lack of monitoring and law enforcement, milk adulteration is more common in developing countries like Bangladesh. The current investigation revealed that overall nutritional quality and composition of both raw and pasteurize milk was more than average but not satisfactory. In this study, majority percent of the milk samples were adulterated with neutralizers which is very alarming. Skimmed milk powder was also found in the milk samples whereas detergent and starch was not detected in any samples. These could be a great health concern for the local people. Awareness, access to information, proper monitoring can be subsidiary to control this unethical practice.

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Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interests in this research.

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